

OF THE ARAB AND AFRICA IMPACT CRATERING AND ASTROGEOLOGY CONFERENCE (AICAC V)

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OF THE ARAB AND AFRICA IMPACT CRATERING AND ASTROGEOLOGY CONFERENCE (AICAC)

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The Department of Earth Science, University of Ghana

In partnership with

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AFRICAN INITIATIVE
FOR PLANETARY AND
SPACE SCIENCE (AFIPS)

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Editors: Marian Selorm Sapah, David Baradoux, Elikplim Dzikunoo

THEMATIC SESSIONS:

- Bosumtwi impact crater
- Impact structures and ejecta
- Meteorites - properties and flux
- Solar System exploration

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Acknowledgement

On behalf of the Organizing Committee of the 5th Edition of the Arab and Africa Impact Cratering and Astrogeology Conference (AICAC V), we wish to extend our deepest appreciation to all those whose contributions have made this event a resounding success. The successful planning and execution of this important gathering would not have been possible without the generous support, unwavering commitment, and collaborative spirit of numerous individuals and organizations across the globe.

We are especially grateful to our esteemed sponsors and institutional partners for their invaluable financial and logistical support, which has been instrumental in bringing this conference to Ghana and enabling broad participation. Their partnership reflects a shared commitment to advancing planetary science, impact cratering research, and astrogeological studies across Africa.

Our sincere thanks go to the members of the Local Organizing Committee, the International Scientific Committee, and all supporting teams who have dedicated significant time and energy to the meticulous planning, coordination, and execution of this event. Their professionalism, attention to detail, and passion for planetary sciences are deeply appreciated.

We acknowledge with gratitude the enthusiastic response from the international scientific community, particularly those who submitted abstracts for both oral and poster presentations. The diversity and quality of the submissions are a testament to the dynamic and evolving nature of impact cratering and planetary science research.

Special recognition is due to the Department of Earth Science, University of Ghana for hosting this event, the African Initiative for Planetary and Space Science (AFIPS) for a solid partnership and to the local government, chiefs and communities around Lake Bosumtwi for their hospitality during our field excursion.

To all our partners, participants, speakers, facilitators, exhibitors, and volunteers, we thank you for your presence, your contributions, and your continued engagement with the advancement of impact cratering and planetary sciences. Your support and collaboration are what truly define the spirit and success of AICAC V.

With heartfelt appreciation, we thank each and every one of you.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgement.....	i
Table of Contents.....	ii
A message from the Chairperson of the Local Organizing Committee.....	v
Committees.....	vii
Programme Outline.....	viii

Special Introduction Section on Bosumtwi

Impact Crater.....	1
1. THE BOSUMTWI IMPACT STRUCTURE: AN OVERVIEW.....	1
2. RECENT GEOLOGICAL AND GEOPHYSICAL INVESTIGATIONS AT BOSUMTWI.....	3

Bosumtwi Impact Crater.....	5
3. THE EXTENSION OF THE CÔTE D'IVOIRE TEKTITE STREWN FIELD AND THE SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF IVORITES.....	5
4. IRON OXIDATION STATE AND COORDINATION ENVIRONMENT IN BRAZILIAN TEKTITES.....	7

Impact structures and ejecta.....	9
5. INTEGRATED STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND 3D SEISMIC DATA: IMPLICATIONS ON THE ENDOGENIC ORIGIN OF THE CIRCULAR MAÂDNA STRUCTURE (TALEMZANE, ALGERIA).....	9
6. INTO THE NADIR: DRILLING AN EXCEPTIONALLY PRESERVED CRETACEOUS-PALEOGENE AGED MARINE IMPACT CRATER OFFSHORE WEST AFRICA.....	11
7. THE VELINGARA STRUCTURE.....	13
8. QUARTZ DEFORMATION AND MELT CONTENT OF THE VICTORIA ISLAND, CANDIDATE IMPACT STRUCTURE.....	15
9. ADDITIONAL TYPES OF SHOCKED ROCKS IN DHALA IMPACT STRUCTURE, INDIA: A FIRST REPORT.....	17

10. ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY TOMOGRAPHY AND VERTICAL ELECTRICAL SOUNDING INVESTIGATION OF HYDROTHERMAL ALTERATION IN THE ZUNGERU STRUCTURE, NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR GROUNDWATER AND MINERAL EXPLORATION.....	20
11. DELLEN CRATER IMPACT MELT ROCK: PYROXENES AS PROXY FOR THE MELT THERMAL HISTORY AND WATER CONTENT.....	23
12. EFFECT OF PREEXISTING TECTONIC FEATURES ON IMPACT FRACTURING AT AMGUID AND TALEMZANE (ALGERIA) PRELIMINARY RESULTS.....	25
Meteorites - properties and flux.....	27
13. Keynote 1: BUILDING METEORITE SCIENCE IN AFRICA - INSIGHTS FROM THE MOROCCAN MODEL.....	27
14. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF METEORITE TERRESTRIAL WEATHERING: REGIONAL TRENDS IN MINERALOGY AND GEOCHEMISTRY.....	29
15. THE ORGANIC COMPOSITION OF CARBONACEOUS METEORITE IMPACTORS: IMPLICATION FOR PLANETARY CHEMISTRY.....	31
16. Keynote 2: ONSET OF A HEAVY BOMBARDMENT ON THE EARTH 1.4 GA AGO.....	33
17. IMPACT-INDUCED METAMORPHIC EFFECTS OF HIGH-ALUMINA AUGITE IN LUNAR ANORTHOSITE BRECCIAS FROM CHANG'E6 LUNAR SOILS.....	35
18. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF A METEORITE COLLECTION FROM EGYPT.....	37
19. CHARACTERIZATION OF ABA PANU METEORITE FALL SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA.....	38
Solar System exploration.....	39
20. Keynote 3: POSSIBLE IMPACT SPHERULE BEDS OBSERVED BY PERSEVERANCE ROVER ON THE RIM OF JEZERO IMPACT CRATER.....	39
21. FROM IMPACT TO DEPOSITION: MARTIAN CRATERS AS SEDIMENTARY THEATERS OF A ONCE-FLUVIAL PLANET.....	41
22. PLANETARY DEFENSE AND SOME ASPECTS OF THE ESA HERA SPACE MISSION.....	43

23. PHASE A FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A SECOND LAGRANGE POINT MARS OBSERVATORY: GLOBAL ATMOSPHERIC ESCAPE, AURORA AND RECONNECTION INVESTIGATION.....	45
24. STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A 1P POCKETQUBE SATELLITE FRAME.....	47
25. THE AFRICAN SPACE STATION PROJECT: BRIDGING THE GAP IN SPACE SCIENCE EDUCATION WITH A VIRTUAL LEARNING PLATFORM FOR STUDENTS IN AFRICA.....	48
Posters	50
26. IRON OXIDATION STATE IN IMPACT GLASS SPHERULES FROM THE BOSUMTWI UPPERMOST IMPACT FALLBACK LAYER.....	50
27. PRELIMINARY PRESENTATION OF SIX POTENTIAL NEW IMPACT SITES DETECTED BY SYSTEMATIC PROSPECTION OF CIRCULAR STRUCTURES IN MAURITANIA.....	52

A Message from the Chairperson of the Local Organizing Committee

Dr. Marian Selorm Sapah

Senior Lecturer, Department of Earth Science,
University of Ghana

Distinguished guests and colleagues, young researchers and students, members of the planetary and space science community and the general public.

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to the 5th Edition of the Arab and Africa Impact Cratering and Astrogeology Conference (AICAC V), being held here in Accra, Ghana, from the 9th to 11th November 2025. On behalf of the entire local and international scientific organizing committees, you are welcome to what promises to be an impactful, insightful and exciting an event.

This conference marks a significant and deliberate milestone. Building on the success of previous editions in North Africa and the visionary decision made in Algiers during AICAC IV, AICAC V is the first to be held in Sub-Saharan Africa. This expansion from the Arab world to encompass the entire continent reflects our collective commitment to decentralizing planetary and space science and ensuring Africa is an active, contributing partner in the global quest to understand our Solar System. Ghana is proud to be at the forefront of this new chapter.

The conference is organized by the Department of Earth Science, University of Ghana in partnership with the African Initiative for Planetary and Space Science (AFIPS). Our gathering here in Accra is more than just a conference. It is a catalyst for our vision to build local capacity and inspire the next generation of planetary and space scientists, through scientific discussions, international collaborations and networking.

The scientific core of AICAC V will be robust, featuring leading international experts, cutting-edge discussions on impact cratering, meteorites, and planetary evolution and space science exhibitions. However, the crown jewel of our programme will be the four-day field excursion to the magnificent Bosumtwi Impact Crater. This natural laboratory, recently designated as one of the second 100 IUGS Geological Heritage Sites, offers an unparalleled opportunity for hands-on learning in one of the world's most pristine and well-preserved impact

structures. To study impact cratering here, on site, is an experience that simply cannot be replicated.

Beyond the science, Accra awaits you with its renowned warm hospitality. You will find a vibrant city rich in culture, history, and a captivating energy.

We look forward to sharing groundbreaking research, building lasting partnerships, and together, advancing the frontiers of impact cratering and astrogeology.

Committees

Organizing Committee

Member	Affiliation
Marian Selorm Saphah (Chair)	University of Ghana
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Marian Selorm Saphah	University of Ghana, Accra, Ghana
Myriam Telus	University of California, Santa Cruz, USA

Programme Outline

Sunday 9th November, 2025 - SEMINAR ROOM NB 11

Pre-conference workshop (pre-registration is mandatory)			
13h00-13h30	Diagnostic criteria for meteoritic impact craters	Search for impact structures - methods	David BARATOUX
13h30-14h00		Macroscopic criteria (shatter cones, meteorites)	David BARATOUX
14h00-14h30		Petrological and geochemical criteria	Christian KOEBERL
14h30-15h00		Examination of tektites and shatter cones and discussion	All
15h00-15h30	Coffee break		
15h30-16h00	Meteorites	Criteria for the identification of meteorites	Hasna CHENNAOUI-AOUDJEHANE and Christian KOEBERL
16h00-16h30		Classification of meteorites	Hamed POURHORSANDI
16h30-17h00		Examination of meteorite samples and discussion	All

Monday 10th November, 2025 SEMINAR ROOM NB 11

8h00-9h00	Registration - welcome		
9h00-9h15	Opening ceremony	Welcome and introductions	Moderator, Abigail AYIKWEI
9h15-9h30		Welcome and short remarks from Chair of LOC	Chair, LOC, Marian Selorm SAPAH
9h30-9h45		Short remarks from the Chairperson of the event	HoD DES, UG, Prince Ofori AMPONSAH
9h45-10h00		Guest speaker	Provost CBAS, UG, Sandow Mark YIDANA
10h00-10h15		Guest speaker (partner institution)	Director GSSTI, GAEC, Joseph Bremang TANDO

10h15-10h30		Guest speaker (partner institution)	President GSAf, Gbenga OKUNTOLA*
10h30-11h00	Photo Session + Coffee break		
11h00-11h40	Special Introductory Session on the Bosumtwi impact crater	The Bosumtwi impact structure: an overview	Christian KOEBERL
11h40-12h20		Recent geological and geophysical investigations at Bosumtwi	David BARATOUX
12h20-13h50	Lunch Break		
13h50-14h10	Bosumtwi impact crater	The extension of the Côte d'Ivoire tektite strewn field and the spatial distribution of ivorites	Petanki SORO
14h10-14h30		Iron oxidation state and coordination environment in Brazilian tektites	Gabriele GIULI
14h30-14h50	Impact structures and ejecta	Integrated structural analysis and 3D seismic data: implications on the endogenic origin of the circular Maâdna structure (Talemzane, Algeria)	Atmane LAMALI
14h50-15h10		Into the Nadir: drilling an exceptional preserved Cretaceous-Paleogene aged marine impact crater offshore West Africa	Uisdean NICHOLSON*
15h10-15h30	Coffee break		
15h30-15h50	Impact structures and ejecta	The Velingara structure	Cheikh Ahmadou Bamba NIANG
15h50-16h10		Quartz deformation and melt content of the Victoria Island impact structure	Myriam TELUS
16h10-16h30		Newer domains of shocked rocks in Dhala impact structure, India: A first report	Anuj K. SINGH
16h30-16h50		Dellen crater impact melt rock: pyroxenes as proxy for the melt thermal history and water content	Sabrina NAZZARENI
16h50-19h00	Telescopes and Skygazing		

Tuesday 11th November, 2025 SEMINAR ROOM 2

8h00-9h00	Registration - welcome		
9h00-9h40	Meteorites - properties and flux	Keynote 1: Building Meteorite Science in Africa - Insights from the Moroccan Model	Hasnaa CHENNAOUI-AOUDJEHANE
9h40-10h00		Comparative study of meteorite terrestrial weathering: regional trends in mineralogy and geochemistry	Hamed POURKHORSANDI
10h00-10h20		The organic composition of meteorite impactors: implication for planetary chemistry	George COOPER*
10h20-10h40	Coffee break		
10h40-11h20	Meteorites - properties and flux	Keynote 2: Onset of a heavy bombardment on the earth 1.4 Ga ago	Anthony LAGAIN
11h20-11h40		Impact-induced metamorphic effects of high-alumina augite in lunar anorthosite breccias from Chang' E 6 lunar soils	Jiawei ZHAO
11h40-12h00		Physical properties of some meteorite collection from Egypt	Bassem S. NABAWY
12h00-12h20		Characterization of Aba Panu meteorite fall south western Nigeria	Gbenga OKUNLOLA*
12h30-14h00	Lunch Break		
14h00-14h30	Solar System exploration	Keynote 3: Possible impact spherule beds observed by perseverance rover on the rim of Jezero impact crater	Nicolas MANGOLD*
14h30-14h50		From impact to deposition: Martian Craters as sedimentary theaters of a once-fluvial planet	Wassim FITOURI
14h50-15h10		Planetary defense and some aspects of the ESA Hera space mission	Christian KOEBERL
15h10-15h30		Phase A mission feasibility study of L2 Mars observatory abstract	Jennifer DARKO
15h30-15h50		Structural design and analysis of a 1p pocketcube satellite frame	Jake YAWSON (first author: Solomon K. Appekey)

15h50-16h10		The African space station project: bridging the gap in space science education with a virtual learning platform for students in Africa	Joshua UZOCHUKWU
16h10-16h40	Coffee break		
16h40-17h00		General information and logistics of the field excursion to Lake Bosumtwi	David BARATOUX, Christian KOEBERL, Marian Selorm SAPAH
17h00-17h30	Closing Ceremony	Closing remarks and vote of thanks	Chairperson of event, Prince Ofori AMPONSAH and Cyril BOATENG

Posters and Exhibitions

Monday 10th- Tuesday 11th November, 2025

SEMINAR ROOM 1

9h00-17h30	Posters and Exhibitions	Iron oxidation state in impact glass spherules from the Bosumtwi uppermost impact fallback layer	Gabriele GIULI
		Preliminary presentation of six potential new impact sites detected by systematic prospection of circular structures in Mauritania	Elycheikh OULD MOHAMED NAVIEE
		Falling whispers visual arts exhibition	Jimas AMETONOU
		CanSat and PocketQube exhibition	Xavier Space Solutions
		Telescope exhibition	Celestron LLC

Special introductory session on Bosumtwi

1. THE BOSUMTWI IMPACT STRUCTURE: AN OVERVIEW

Christian Koeberl*

*'Department of Lithospheric Research, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna,
Austria*

Abstract

Bosumtwi is one of only about 20 currently confirmed African impact craters, is associated with one of only four known tektite strewn fields (the Ivory Coast tektite strewn field), and is arguably the best-preserved complex young impact structure known on Earth. It has an age of 1.07 million years, is almost completely filled by Lake Bosumtwi of roughly 8.5 km diameter, and has a rim-to-rim diameter of about 10.5 km. There is an outer ring structure of about 18-20 km in diameter, the origin of which is not well understood. The structure is excavated in 2.1-2.2 Ga metasediments and metavolcanics of the Birimian Supergroup. A central uplift is hidden underneath the lake sediments. Lake Bosumtwi has several important characteristics that make it well suited to provide a detailed record of climate change in an equatorial region. The lake developed in a hydrologically closed basin, and the deep water is anoxic, which has led to the preservation of laminated sediment varves in the lake sediments, providing a means for high resolution (annual) paleoclimate reconstruction. Because of its importance for impact geology and paleoclimatology, renewed interest (from the 1990s on) in Bosumtwi led to various studies by several multinational teams, ultimately leading to deep drilling. Remote sensing and geophysical measurements (gravity, magnetics, reflection and refraction seismics) provided abundant new data on the crater and its subsurface. This also allowed for correlating geophysical studies and provides material for comparison with tektites and ejected material.

Within the framework of the ICDP project, 16 drill cores were obtained from June to October 2004 at six locations within Lake Bosumtwi. Fourteen sediment cores, representing a total of 1833 m aggregate length completely sampled the Quaternary to Recent lake sediments, and two continuous deep cores with a total length of ca. 360 m were obtained from the impactites and underlying basement. In addition, extensive geophysical studies were carried out. The 14 sediment cores were investigated for paleoenvironmental indicators. The two impactite cores, LB-07A and LB-08A, were drilled into the deepest section of the annular moat (540 m) and the flank of the central uplift (450 m), respectively. Samples from these cores have been studied by more than a dozen different research teams from around the world. A set of peer-reviewed papers resulting from this work has been published in 2007 in a special issue of the journal "Meteoritics and Planetary Science".

This presentation will provide an overview of Bosumtwi as an impact crater, the drilling project, and also review more recent research and developments. Aside from its importance for impact crater and paleoclimate studies, the crater lake is of local spiritual interest and is an economic source of fish and tourism. As such it is also noticeable that nearby (unauthorized) gold mining may contaminate the lake. It is a striking geographical feature with potential for outreach and education, and all this recently led to it being designated an IUGS Geoheritage site: https://iugs-geoheritage.org/geoheritage_sites/lake-bosumtwi-impact-crater/.

Keywords: Bosumtwi; Drilling Projects; Tektites

**Corresponding author: christian.koeberl@univie.ac.at*

2. RECENT GEOLOGICAL AND GEOPHYSICAL INVESTIGATIONS AT BOSUMTWI

David Baratoux^{1*}, Marian Selorm Sapah², Cyril Boateng³, Minoru Uehara⁴,
Régis Braucher⁴

¹*Géosciences Environnement Toulouse, CNRS, IRD & Université de
Toulouse, France*

²*Department of Earth Science, University of Ghana, Accra, Ghana.*

³*Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi,
Ghana.*

⁴*Aix-Marseille Univ, CNRS, IRD, INRAE, CEREGE, Aix-en-Provence, France*

Abstract

The Bosumtwi impact structure formed 1.07 Ma ago in 2.1 – 2.2 old greenschist-facies metasedimentary rocks is one of the best-preserved impact craters on Earth. An enigmatic ring pattern in potassium (K) concentrations was noted in an airborne radiometric survey [1]. Its post-impact origin (erosion and weathering) was recently elucidated using a portable spectroradiometer, which distinguished between K-rich freshly exposed metasediments and K-poor weathered rock and regolith [2]. This study also demonstrated that the morphology of the ejecta, characterized by an annular moat and ridge, is analogous to fluidized, water-rich ejecta observed on Mars, commonly referred to as rampart craters. Our hypothesis, that erosion and weathering were largely controlled by the initial topography of the crater, is supported by cosmogenic nuclides analyses and, independently, by numerical modelling [3]. This discovery led to the identification of other rampart craters on Earth (Wulf & Kenkmann, 2021). More samples were collected on the crater rim, moat and distal ridge in 2025 with passive seismic experiment (H/V method) to better constrain the variations of ejecta

thicknesses and erosion rates. Deforestation linked to artisanal gold mining activities was also observed in the region and mapped. The use of hazardous chemicals such as mercury and cyanide for ore processing, common in West African artisanal mining practices, poses risks of contamination to both the water of Lake Bosumtwi and its aquatic life. Our recent investigations at Bosumtwi underscore its significance across multiple disciplines: impact science, geomorphology, as well as environmental, societal, and public health fields.

References

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Keywords: Bosumtwi, Cosmogenic nuclides, Passive Seismology, Ejecta, Erosion, Weathering

**Corresponding author David.baratoux@ird.fr*

Bosumtwi Impact Crater

3. THE EXTENSION OF THE CÔTE D'IVOIRE TEKTITE STREWN FIELD AND THE SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF IVORITES.

Petanki Soro^{1,2*}, Pierre Rochette², David Baratoux^{1,3}, Alain N. Kouamelan¹

¹*Félix Houphouët-Boigny University, Abidjan-Cocody, Côte d'Ivoire*

²*Aix-Marseille University, CEREGE, CNRS, IRD, Aix-en-Provence, France*

³*Toulouse University, GET, CNRS & IRD, Toulouse, France*

Abstract

The tektite field in Côte d'Ivoire, whose tektites are called 'ivoirites', was formed following the Bosumtwi meteorite impact, which occurred 1.07 million years ago in southern Ghana. Since its discovery in 1935 and the few field missions carried out between 1960 and 1970, this tektite field has been the subject of very few exploration missions.

Current research into tektites in this field is hampered by several factors, such as dense vegetation cover, difficult access to certain areas, the difficulty of conducting very large systematic research campaigns, and the local population's lack of knowledge about these objects.

Between 2019 and 2023, new exploration missions were conducted, aiming to extend the previously described tektite field, as well as areas beyond its historical boundaries. In order to facilitate the discovery of new specimens of ivorite, a participatory research approach has been adopted with the local population. Representatives of local communities have been made aware of the true nature and origin of the small black stones they found in their fields. Volunteer residents have been trained to survey the local population and record potential new discoveries of tektites. This approach

has resulted in the collection of 174 new samples of ivorite and the expansion of the tektite field in Côte d'Ivoire from 1,500 km² to 4,100 km² [4]. These new discoveries, combined with the availability of increasingly accurate topographic data in the region, make it possible to study the geomorphological processes that may have affected this tektite field since its formation. The FABDEM-v2 global topographic data, supported by a cosmonuclides study of ¹⁰Be and ²⁶Al, have made it possible to quantify various relief parameters, such as roughness, slope and azimuth, at different scales, and to propose a model of the geomorphological evolution of the tektite field since its formation.

References

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Keywords: Ivorites, Bosumtwi impact crater, Côte d'Ivoire, Geomorphology, cosmonuclides.

**Corresponding author. petanksoro@gmail.com*

4. IRON OXIDATION STATE AND COORDINATION ENVIRONMENT IN BRAZILIAN TEKTITES

Gabriele Giuli^{*}, Valeria Desantis¹, Alvaro P. Crosta², Gabriel Gonçalves³,
Ludovic Ferriere⁴,

¹*School of Science and Technology–Geology Div., University of Camerino,
Italy*

²*Istituto de Geociencias, Universidade CAmpinas, Campinas, Brasil*

³*Instituto de Química, Universidade de São Paulo (USP), São Paulo, Brasil*

⁴*Natural History Museum, Abu Dhabi, EAU*

Abstract

Recently, ca. 500 samples of tektites from the Minas Gerais state (Brazil) have been reported. The glass is mostly homogeneous, occasionally showing lechatelierite inclusions. In terms of chemical composition, it falls in the dacite and rhyolite fields of the total alkali versus silica diagram, with similar SiO₂ and slightly higher Na₂O+K₂O content in comparison with other known tektites.

In order to get information on the iron oxidation state of these samples, we performed micro-XANES measurements.

The samples used for XANES measurements have been prepared as polished thin sections or polished slides. XANES data have been collected at the Carnaúba beamline of the SIRIUS ring of the Brazilian Synchrotron Light Laboratory (Campinas, Brazil) using a Si (111) monochromator. The small X-ray beam size allowed it to probe several spots for each sample. Accurate analysis of the pre-edge peak energy and integrated intensity allowed to determine Fe³⁺/(Fe²⁺+Fe³⁺) ratios on all samples with an estimated error of ±0.05 [2].

XANES data collected on 5 different samples display a good signal to noise ratio, allowing to extract information on the Fe oxidation state from the pre-edge region. The energy and integrated intensity of the pre-edge peak indicate that Fe is mostly divalent in these samples, with Fe³⁺ / (Fe²⁺

+ Fe³⁺) ratios between 0.0 and 0.1. The pre-edge peak intensity is indicative of a coordination number of divalent Fe intermediate between 4 and 5.

We did not find significant differences in the shape and energy of Fe XANES spectra collected for different samples, nor between spectra collected within the same samples, testifying to the homogeneity of the Fe redox in the analysed tektite samples. Both Fe oxidation state and coordination environment are similar to those of most tektites studied so far [3,4,5] and to Trinity glass [6].

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Keywords: tektites, XANES

*Corresponding author. gabriele.giuli@unicam.it

Impact structures and ejecta

5. INTEGRATED STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND 3D SEISMIC DATA: IMPLICATIONS ON THE ENDOGENIC ORIGIN OF THE CIRCULAR MAÂDNA STRUCTURE (TALEMZANE, ALGERIA)

Atmane Lamali^{1*}, Pierre Rochette², Lamine HAMAI¹, Nacer Eddine Merabet¹,

Said Maouche¹, Mohamed Arab³, Abdeslam. About¹

¹*CRAAG, B.P. 63, Bouzaréah 16340 Alger, Algeria.*

²*Aix-Marseille Université, CNRS, IRD, CEREGE UM34, 13545 Aix en Provence, France*

³*Sonatrach/Exploration Division, Avenue du 1er novembre Bat 'C' BP 68, Boumerdes, Algeria*

Abstract

The Maâdna circular structure in the Sahara Atlas (Algeria) has long been interpreted as a meteorite impact crater (Lambert et al. 1980). However, recent studies (Lamali et al., 2016, 2019, and 2022) have challenged this interpretation, while proposing instead that it has a tectono-sedimentary origin involving the diapiric intrusion of Triassic evaporites. This new analysis is supported by a combination of geophysical, structural, and field evidence, including the presence of tilted Cretaceous strata and radial fault patterns, and basement-rooted lineaments. Unlike previous studies, this one relies on 2D regional seismic profiles and structural reconstructions (e.g., Bracene and Frizon de Lamotte, 2002), this work integrates high-resolution 3D seismic data acquired for hydrocarbon exploration to provide new insights into the deep structure of the Maâdna circular crater. Though earlier interpretations emphasized basement uplift and thickening of the Mesozoic sequences, our data reveal a more localized diapiric mechanism originating from the Triassic evaporites. This mechanism may have played a key role in the formation of the present-day relief and structural depression. We also interpret the uplift of the Maâdna structure as a manifestation of a mid-Cretaceous tectonic phase that affected the Sahara Platform, contrary to the traditional view

of its passive tabular subsidence. Integrating 3D seismic imaging with field observations around Maâdna sheds new light on the polyphased evolution of the Sahara platform and questions the basic tectonic models previously applied to this region. This reinterpretation, based on structural configuration related to salt tectonics, highlights the presence of long-wavelength folding that had previously been overlooked in surface geology due to their subtle curvature. Our results offer a "non-impactist" resolution to a decades-old debate. More importantly, they reveal a faulted and folded hydrocarbon-prone domain within an area that has long been considered tectonically stable. Thus, beyond resolving a scientific controversy, this study emphasizes the importance of re-evaluating suspected impact structures in light of advanced geophysical data, and highlights the need for a revised tectonic framework for the central Sahara Platform. Furthermore, it provides a valuable structural model with implications for future resource exploration in the region.

Keywords: Maâdna circular structure, Sahara Platform, Hidden Cretaceous tectonics, Diapirism, 3D seismic data, Non-impact hypothesis.

**Corresponding author. a.lamali@craag.dz; atmane.lamali@gmail.com*

6. INTO THE NADIR: DRILLING AN EXCEPTIONALLY PRESERVED CRETACEOUS–PALEOGENE AGED MARINE IMPACT CRATER OFFSHORE WEST AFRICA

Uisdean Nicholson¹, IODP proposal 1004 proponents

¹ *School of Energy, Geoscience, Infrastructure and Society, Heriot-Watt
University, Edinburgh, UK*

Abstract

The Nadir Crater is an exceptionally well-preserved impact structure situated ~400 km offshore Guinea, West Africa, buried 300 m below the seafloor, in 900 m water depth. First identified from 2D seismic data in 2022, it was proposed as a new candidate near K–Pg-aged marine impact crater [1]. Initial interpretation revealed a crater rim >8.5 km in diameter surrounded by a ~20 km brim, with morphological characteristics consistent with a complex crater. Its discovery is significant, as it may represent an impact event closely coincident to Chicxulub Crater offshore Mexico, raising important questions about the relationship between the two events at the end of the Cretaceous Period.

The crater was subsequently mapped in detail using 3D seismic data [2]. This data covers the entire crater and brim, a first for any terrestrial impact structure, revealing crater architecture in exceptional detail. These data reveal the presence of complex radial faults around the central uplift, and a complex set of normal, reverse and strike-slip faults in the crater moat and brim, allowing the kinematics of crater collapse to be reconstructed. These data also reveal important seismic geomorphological observations at the crater floor, including extensive regional liquefaction associated with seismic shaking, coeval submarine landslides at the margin of the Guinea Plateau, concentric shear ridges caused by tsunami propagation, and resurge scars caused by water cascading back into the evacuated cavity.

Despite these insights from seismic data, key questions remain unresolved, particularly regarding the precise age of the impact, its

environmental effects, and the fundamental physical processes involved in a marine impact such as this. To address these, we have proposed targeted scientific drilling of the Nadir Crater through the International Ocean Discovery Programme (IODP³) [3]. This expedition, now scheduled for drilling in 2027, will allow us to recover continuous core data from the crater floor to the central uplift. These records will provide unique constraints on crater kinematics, impact energy, associated hazards and recovery of marine ecosystems in the aftermath of this event.

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Keywords: Marine crater, K–Pg extinction, crater modification

7. THE VELINGARA STRUCTURE

Cheikh A. B. Niang^{1,2*}, David Baratoux³, Yoann Quesnel⁴, Pierre Rochette⁴,
Makhoudia Fall⁵

¹*Société des Mines du Senegal,*

²*Institut Fondamental d'Afrique Noire, IFAN/Cheikh Anta Diop,*

²*Geosciences Environnement Toulouse, CNRS, Institut de Recherche
pour le Développement (IRD) & Université de Toulouse, 31400, Toulouse,
France,*

⁴*Aix-Marseille Université, CNRS, IRD, INRAE, CEREGE, Aix-en-Provence,
France*

³*Département de Géologie, Université Cheikh Anta DIOP.*

Abstract

The Velingara circular depression also known as the Velingara structure is centered at 13°01'05"N, 14°07'38"W in southern Senegal, about 12 km south-southwest of the homonymous town. The Velingara structure is a 48 km diameter topographic depression identified on Landsat MSS and TM images, and in NOAA- AVHRR imagery (Master et al., 1999). These authors proposed that the structure was buried under post-Eocene continental sediments (Master et al., 1999). We have visited the circular depression twice in 2023 and 2024. Geomorphologically, the structure is flat with low altitude (<70 m above sea level), and there is no outcrop except laterite. Rocks from the basement of the regional Mauritanides Belt sub-crop out in the central part of the structure which has been considered by previous workers as a possible indication of central uplift of a complex crater with a set of faults (Wade et al., 2006; Théveniaut et al., 2010). Niang et al. (2014) noted that the absence of topographic expression in the center of the structure which is not consistent with a complex impact crater. A geophysical survey (gravimetric + magnetic) was carried out by our team in 2022. The survey identified a circular 10 km diameter negative gravity anomaly of 15 mgal at the center of the depression and a significant amplitude magnetic field of 100 nT (Quesnel et al., 2024). The size of the

gravity anomaly is much smaller than the topographic expression raising questions about the actual size of the impact structure (if confirmed). A non-diagnostic single granular zircon was found in a sample of modern alluvium, which closely resembles grains with highly dispersed neoblast orientations that have only been reported from impact settings. A drilling campaign is planned for December 2025 to recover samples below the sedimentary cover. Considering the differences in size of the geophysical and geomorphological expressions, the drilling scenario would involve two locations: the first one will have a total depth of 30 m, with the first 5 m drilled destructively and the remaining 25 m cored, the second will have a total depth of 100 m, with the first 10 m drilled destructively and the remaining 90 m cored.

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Keywords: The Velingara structure, impact, geophysics, drilling, core samples.

*Corresponding author. cabniangeos@gmail.com

8. QUARTZ DEFORMATION AND MELT CONTENT OF THE VICTORIA ISLAND, CANDIDATE IMPACT STRUCTURE.

Myriam Telus^{1*}, Tatum Lexvold¹, Benjamin Otter², Marian Selorm Sapah³,
Sonia M. Tikoo², Anton Ermakov⁴

¹*Earth and Planetary Sciences, University of California Santa Cruz; 1156 High Street, Santa Cruz, CA, 95064, USA,* ²*Geophysics, Stanford University; 397 Panama Mall, Stanford, CA 94305, USA,* ³*Department of Earth Sciences, University of Ghana, Legon, Accra, Ghana.* ⁴*Aeronautics and Astronautics, Stanford University; 397 Panama Mall, Stanford, CA 94305, USA*

Abstract

The Victoria Island *candidate* impact structure is a subsurface feature located in the San Joaquin Valley in Northern California, USA. It is approximately 5.5 km in diameter and has sedimentary shale target rock. The possible crater was first discovered by [1] using 3-D seismic survey and well logs. Sedimentary samples, gathered from a drill core from ~1.3 km to 2 km depths near the center of the structure, were made available to us for analyses to confirm its classification as an impact structure. Thin sections of three different grain sizes (coarse, medium and fine) for each depth were also provided. For this study, we analysed thin sections from depths of 1.58 km to 1.65 km (5170 ft – 5410 ft) using a petrographic microscope to determine the occurrence and frequency of shocked quartz, one of the most defining features of an impact event. Under an optical microscope, shocked quartz grains will show planar deformation features (PDFs), closely spaced (2-10 μm) narrow (2-3 μm) lineations in parallel planar regions [2].

The highest frequency of shocked quartz appears in samples from ~1.58 km (5200 ft) depth. Many PDF grains are not well-defined, making it

difficult to fully identify them as shocked quartz. Geologically old, shocked quartz may have less defined PDFs or what is known as decorated PDFs, where fluid inclusions form along the PDFs. PDFs can also fade over time due to alteration and metamorphism of the quartz. Additionally, thin sections from 1.58 km depth consists of significantly more melt-like particles compared to the other layers, potentially consistent with estimates of ~20% melt volume for a crater of this size [3]. Finally, the sediment from 1.58 km depth appears visibly darker than sediment from the other layers, potentially consistent with shock darkening discussed in other studies [4]. Overall, our preliminary results provide further support that the Victoria Island subsurface structure is impact related.

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Keywords: shocked quartz, melt, sedimentary, impact crater

*Corresponding author: [*mtelus@ucsc.edu](mailto:mtelus@ucsc.edu)

9. ADDITIONAL TYPES OF SHOCKED ROCKS IN DHALA IMPACT STRUCTURE, INDIA: A FIRST REPORT

Anuj K. Singh^{1*}, Shivanshu Dwivedi², Jayanta K. Pati^{2,3}

¹*Department of Geology, Nilamber Pitamber University, Medininagar,
Palamu-822102, Jharkhand, India*

²*Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science,
University of Allahabad, Prayagraj-211002, Uttar Pradesh, India*

³*National Centre of Experimental Mineralogy and Petrology, 14 Chatham
Lines, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj-211002, Uttar Pradesh, India*

Abstract

The Dhala structure is the largest impact structure in the Indian subcontinent known so far [1]. It is located in the western periphery of Bundelkhand craton, north-central India. The target rocks of the Dhala structure predominantly consist of granitoids and their various textural variants (e.g. syeno- and monzogranites, diorites, granodiorites, etc.). Amongst the impact-affected rocks, a wide variety of breccia (e.g., monomict granitoid breccia, polymict lithic breccia, suevite breccia, impact melt breccia, brecciated quartz reef, and pseudotachylitic breccia) is observed across both surface and subsurface exposures. The earlier studies on the Dhala structure had focused primarily on a limited subset of these rocks, especially impact melt breccias and suevite breccia, documenting a wide spectrum of diagnostic shock metamorphic features [1, 2]. However, a significant number of breccia types and other lithological units have remained underexplored. Here, we report the first evidence of shock metamorphism from the monomict granitoid breccia, polymict lithic breccia, and brecciated Giant Quartz Vein (GQV).

Five representative samples of each breccia type were selected from locations situated about 3.8 to 5.8 km radially outward from the central elevated area (CEA) of the Dhala impact structure, and thirty polished thin-sections were studied. Single to multiple sets of PDFs and PFs are observed in quartz (\pm K-feldspar) in all types of breccia samples along

with mosaicism, fractured zircon, and kinked biotite. The polymict lithic breccia comprises angular to subangular clasts from diverse target lithologies (e.g. granitoid, diorite, rhyolite, gabbro, amphibolite, calc-silicate, and quartzite) in a fine-grained clastic matrix. They are classified into four classes based on colour of the matrix and clast composition; Type-1: Polymict lithic breccia with a dark brown to brownish-red matrix; Type-2: Polymict lithic breccia with lithic and mineral clasts within a greenish-grey matrix; Type-3: Polymict lithic breccia with lithic and mineral clasts within a reddish-yellow matrix; and Type-4: Polymict lithic breccia with lithic and mineral clasts within a reddish orange to pale brown matrix. A few brecciated outcrops of quartz reefs are well-exposed in the Dhala area, especially in the northwest, south and southeast of the CEA. The reefs are intensely fractured and jointed in nature. Most joints have steep dips, with an average dip value of $\sim 80^\circ$ towards the NE-NNE direction in the SW part of the structure. In places, ridge offsets by up to 100 m across the normal strike of GQV is observed. The quartz in these reefs is milky white to light grey to greenish in colour, crystalline in nature, and contains sericite. It displays brecciation, zoning, polygonization, and undulatory extinction. Occasionally, a few quartz grains exhibit dynamic recrystallization in the form of subgrain development. The impact melt breccia from the Dhala structure exhibits a wide range of textures, and are grouped as clast-rich, clast-poor, and clast-free varieties based on their clast proportions.

Thus, the present study identifies spatially varied newer lithological domains of shocked rocks in the Dhala structure, extending up to 5.8 km radial distance from the CEA. This further implies that the Dhala structure possess a larger diameter than previously estimated. The evidence of diagnostic shock features across multiple lithologies confirms a broader spatial extent and high peak shock pressure above 30 GPa, further emphasizing the preservation potential for shock features in pre-Paleozoic terrains worldwide. In addition, the field evidence, including the first observation of shocked quartz grains within some quartz reef outcrops in and around the Dhala area, supports their pre-impact origin, setting an upper age limit for the impact event around 2.1 Ga. The stratigraphic correlation with overlying sedimentary units further

constrains the minimum age of the Dhala structure between 1.78 and 1.93 Ga, establishing it as the Earth's third oldest known impact structure, after Yarrabubba (Australia) and Vredefort (South Africa).

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Keywords: Dhala impact structure, shock metamorphism, monomict breccia, polymict breccia, quartz, PDFs

**Corresponding author. anujpcb@gmail.com*

10. EFFECT OF PREEXISTING TECTONIC FEATURES ON IMPACT FRACTURING AT AMGUID AND TALEMZANE (ALGERIA) PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Ratiba SAHOUI¹ and Djelloul BELHAI¹

¹University of Sciences and Technology Houari boumedienne, Algiers, Algeria

Abstract

Introduction: Amguid (450m) and Talemzane (1750m) are simple, well-preserved young craters in Algeria (Sahoui 2024). The craters affect different pre-impact target rock structures providing an opportunity to assess the impact fracturing and the preexisting tectonic features relationship. In addition, they are situated within a vast geological region with significant hydrocarbon potential, this study will thus contribute to understand the deformation pattern in sedimentary target rocks as well as its effect on the petroleum reservoirs they have affected.

Pre-impact target rock structure: to assess the tectonic features affecting the target rocks, a combination of remote sensing and geological maps study is undertaken; a lineament map has been realized. Amguid and Talemzane are well-preserved craters in the arid regions of the Saharan platform. Amguid is situated to the south area of this domain characterized by Lower Devonian sandstones with a 20° monoclinial dip toward the northwest and is affected by precambrian N-S large-scale shear zones that were reactivated during the Holocene. At Talemzane, target rocks are characterized by horizontal bedding Upper Cretaceous to Eocene limestones and flint planes of the north of the Saharan platform, that are cut by at least two prominent sets of pre-impact tectonic fracture systems: the major N-S shear zones as well as less prominent E-W sets in relationship with jurassic opening of the atlasic basin.

Outline: the two craters can be easily identified using the TanDEM-X digital elevation model as the areas are devoid of vegetation cover and distant from sand dunes. Amguid has an almost quadrangular form with

well-observable E-W, NW-SE and NNE- SSW edges while Talemzane is circular with gentle NW- SE and NE- SW edges to the south of the structure. The preexisting tectonic joint sets are oriented diagonally to the straight segments of the craters outlines, this is attested by the absence of E-W edges at Talemzane. The primary reasons for the polygonal shape of craters are regional joint sets that delineate parts of the craters (Kenkmann, 2021). According to Poelchau et al. (2009), this joints' diagonal orientation facilitates more efficient crater excavation in simple structures.

Fracturation: the Amguid's and Talemzane's rims are cut by two distinct groups of fractures: radial and concentric. At Talemzane, radial fractures are well-visible on TanDEM-X digital elevation model, Field Numerical Model that we have realized using altitudes measurements and panoramic pictures of the crater. The radial fractures have subvertical dips and strike approximately perpendicular to the bedding planes or obliquely, occurring as conjugate pairs. This study reports over 125 measurements of faults and fractures orientations on 11 points around the crater wall. Great circles and poles density contours allowed the deduction of divergent stress from the crater center due to the shock waves propagation during the excavation stage. At Amguid, these subvertical radial fractures are only visible on field; they are few centimeters spaced apart but are not organized as conjugate pairs. The N-S and E-W preexisting tectonic fractures have controlled the conjugate pairs pattern at Talemzane while the N-S ones are responsible for a single set of radial fractures at Amguid. The well-developed concentric fractures strike more or less parallel to the bedding planes. At Talemzane, the concentric fractures are cut by radial dikes, which mean that the concentric fractures are formed prior to the radial ones.

Conclusions: Amguid's and Talemzane's walls are crosscut at least by two prominent sets of fractures: radials and concentric, these are similar to the types of fractures that occur at Meteor Crater and Lonar Crater (Kummar et al. 2008). The radial fractures organization (conjugate pairs or not) is controlled by preexisting tectonic features, they are formed after the concentric fractures at Talemzane. The pre-impact joints have

contributed to the polygonal shapes of the craters and facilitated more efficient crater excavation.

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Keywords: *impact fracturing; Amguid; Talemzane; tectonic joints; outline.*

*Corresponding author: r.sahoui@gmail.com

11. DELLEN CRATER IMPACT MELT ROCK: PYROXENES AS PROXY FOR THE MELT THERMAL HISTORY AND WATER CONTENT

Sabrina Nazzareni¹, Gabriele Giuli^{2*}, Henrik Skogby³

*¹Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, della Vita e della
Sostenibilità Ambientale*

Università di Parma, Parma, Italy

*²School of Science and Technology–Geology Div., University of
Camerino, Italy*

*³Swedish Museum of Natural History, Department of Geosciences, SE-
10405 Stockholm, Sweden*

Abstract

The Dellen impact structure is located in a ca. 20 km wide basin filled by two lakes in the east central Sweden. This complex structure is covered by a thick moraine deposit, and most impact melted material can be found as loose blocks and boulders scattered throughout the moraine. Geophysical measurements show the presence of a coherent impact melt body about 9 km in diameter and 200 to 500 m thick [1] for which impact ages ranging between 90, 110, to 140 Ma have been determined (2,3 and references therein). Here we describe the petrography and mineral chemistry of an impact melt glass (commonly referred to as dellenite) consisting of phenocrysts of subhedral orthopyroxene (average $Wo_4En_{63}Fs_{33}$), skeletal plagioclase (average $An_{59}Ab_{38}Or_3$), and euhedral magnetite within a glassy matrix of rhyolitic composition.

MicroFTIR measurements performed both in the glass matrix and in the euhedral glass blebs within the skeletal plagioclase show the presence of 1.4 wt% water in the rhyolitic glass. Comparing the water content of the glass with the water solubility of a silicate melt with the same composition as determined by the model by Papale [4], suggests that the studied sample vitrified at a pressure of about 200–300 bar.

Orthopyroxene crystals from the dellenite sample were studied by polarized FTIR spectroscopy, Mössbauer spectroscopy, single crystal X-ray diffraction and electron probe micro analysis. Dellenite

orthopyroxenes are iron rich enstatite ($\text{Wo}_4 \text{En}_{63} \text{Fs}_{33}$) with a $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}_{\text{tot}}$ ratio of 1.6%, as measured by Mößbauer spectroscopy. The studied orthopyroxenes have very weak to absent OH vibrational bands in the IR spectra, corresponding to H_2O contents ranging from 0 to 39 ppm H_2O . These variable contents seem to indicate H loss during post-formation processes, which may occur via the relatively fast redox reaction $\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{OH}^- = \text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{O}^{2-} + \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2$.

In order to restore H that was possibly lost, dellenite pyroxenes were thermally annealed under hydrogen atmosphere (at 1 Atm) in a horizontal glass-tube furnace at the Department of Geosciences (Natural History Museum Stockholm). We performed thermal annealing experiments at 700°C for 17 hours. FTIR spectra were recorded after each heating step. All the samples increased their hydrogen content and the final average water content is 77 ppm.

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Keywords: impact melt glass, water content, micro-FTIR

*Corresponding author. gabriele.giuli@unicam.it

12. ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY TOMOGRAPHY AND VERTICAL ELECTRICAL SOUNDING INVESTIGATION OF HYDROTHERMAL ALTERATION IN THE ZUNGERU STRUCTURE, NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR GROUNDWATER AND MINERAL EXPLORATION

Mfoniso U. Aka¹, Okechukwu E. Agbasi², Johnson C. Ibuot³

¹Federal University of Technology, Ikot Abasi, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, Department of Physics; ²Heritage Polytechnic, Eket Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, Department of Science Laboratory Technology; ³University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria Department of Physics & Astronomy.

Abstract

The Zungeru Structure in Niger State, north-central Nigeria, lies within the Kuseriki Schist Belt of the Precambrian Basement Complex and is intersected by the Kalangai–Zungeru–Ifewara transcurrent fault system. The origin of the structure has been debated, but its intense fracturing and brecciation suggest a possible impact-related deformation, which could have initiated hydrothermal alteration, enhanced fluid circulation, and localized mineralization. This study aims to (i) map hydrothermal alteration zones within the Zungeru Structure, (ii) evaluate their potential for groundwater storage and ore mineralization, and (iii) develop a geophysical workflow applicable to African impact-like structures. Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) for high-resolution lateral imaging of subsurface resistivity patterns and Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) for depth-specific profiling methods will be employed. Data acquisition employed a Wenner–Schlumberger array for ERT and Schlumberger configuration for VES. Profiles were integrated with structural field mapping, Landsat-8 OLI remote sensing, Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) DEM analysis, and aeromagnetic interpretation to identify lineaments and alteration trends. ERT sections delineated conductive zones ($< 50 \Omega\cdot\text{m}$) interpreted as clay-rich breccias, fracture networks, and possible mineralized alteration halos. VES curves distinguished unaltered

basement ($> 500 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$) from conductive alteration zones and saturated deposits. Identified conductive corridors align with NNE–SSW and NE–SW fault trends, coinciding with mapped hydrothermal zones and artisanal gold workings. These features indicate potential for both fracture-controlled aquifers and economic mineralization (Au, Ni–Cu–PGE, REEs). Results demonstrate that integrated ERT–VES surveys can effectively detect post-impact or impact-analogue hydrothermal systems. The findings support sustainable resource development in Zungeru through targeted groundwater exploration and mineral assessment. Furthermore, the study contributes to understanding the broader role of moderate-sized impacts in reshaping local hydrology, concentrating economic minerals, and influencing environmental evolution in African cratonic terrains.

Keywords: Zungeru Structure, impact structure, Electrical Resistivity Tomography, groundwater, mineral exploration

**Corresponding author: mfonisoaka@futia.edu.ng*

Meteorites - properties and flux

Keynote 1

13. BUILDING METEORITE SCIENCE IN AFRICA – INSIGHTS

FROM THE MOROCCAN MODEL

Hasnaa Chennaoui Aoudjehane^{1,2,3}

¹GeoPen Laboratory, Hassan II University of Casablanca, Faculty of Science Ain Chok, km8 route d'El Jadida 20150 Casablanca Morocco

hassna.chennaoui@univh2c.ma*

²Institute for Advanced Studies, UM6P Benguerir Morocco

³ATTARIK Foundation for Meteoritics and Planetary Science, Morocco

Abstract

North Africa has become an increasingly important region for planetary sciences due to the significant number of meteorites discovered across the continent. Morocco represents a particularly rich case, with systematic recoveries since 1999 positioning the country among the leading sources worldwide. These meteorites constitute both a major scientific resource and a valuable geoheritage.

At Hassan II University of Casablanca, meteorite research was integrated into academic curricula and developed from early studies of Martian meteorites to broader investigations encompassing all classes, impact cratering, and Martian surface geology. This development was structured through a quadripartite approach combining research, academic training, communication and outreach. It also contributed to the establishment of key initiatives such as the Africa Initiative for Planetary and Space Sciences (AFIPS) and the ATTARIK Foundation.

The Moroccan experience provides an illustrative example of how meteorite-rich regions can leverage this heritage to advance planetary sciences at the continental scale. In this keynote, I will present data on

meteorite discoveries in Africa, with particular emphasis on Morocco as a model for developing planetary science research, education, and public engagement.

Keywords: Meteorites, Africa, Morocco, Planetary sciences, Geoheritage, outreach.

14. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF METEORITE TERRESTRIAL WEATHERING: REGIONAL TRENDS IN MINERALOGY AND GEOCHEMISTRY

Hamed Pourkhorsandi¹, Jérôme Gattacceca², Pierre Rochette², Vinciane Debaille³

¹Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD), Géosciences Environnement Toulouse (GET), CNRS, Université de Toulouse, CNES, Toulouse, France

²CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université, IRD, INRAE, CEREGE, Aix-en-Provence, France

³Laboratoire G-Time, Université libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, Belgium

Abstract

Upon their fall onto Earth's surface, meteorites become contaminated by terrestrial compounds, and their mineralogy undergoes weathering (terrestrial alteration) to equilibrate with the new environment. These weathering effects are reflected in their mineralogical, elemental, and isotopic composition. For a given meteorite with similar structural, textural, mineralogical, and geochemical characteristics, such changes do not necessarily occur in the same way when the meteorites fall in different environments.

The weathering of a meteorite is influenced by both the climate type and the nature of the surface on which it lands [e.g., 1]. Falling in a humid region or on a wet surface accelerates the rate of weathering. For this reason, the terrestrial ages of meteorites differ between regions with different climatic conditions. Antarctica and the Atacama Desert, extreme cold and hot deserts, respectively, are known to host meteorites with the highest terrestrial ages (up to millions of years) [2,3]. In contrast, meteorites from younger deserts such as Lut, the Sahara, or the deserts

of the Arabian Peninsula tend to have shorter terrestrial ages (mainly less than 50,000 years) [4-6].

These differences lead to distinct paths of mineralogical and geochemical weathering. In this presentation, we will provide examples of various weathering effects observed in meteorites collected from different desert environments and discuss the differences between them. Special emphasis will be placed on the trace elemental composition (e.g., REE, Sr, Ba) of meteorites and its usefulness in distinguishing meteorites from different deserts [7].

Additionally, we will discuss the impact of weathering on the ^{143}Nd isotopic composition of meteorites collected from the Atacama and Lut deserts and what this reveals about the weathering processes [8]. The implications of meteorite weathering studies for understanding climate will be addressed, along with the prospects for future research and the need for more detailed investigations.

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Keywords: Meteorite, Desert, Weathering

*Corresponding author: hamed.pourkhorsandi@ird.fr

15. THE ORGANIC COMPOSITION OF CARBONACEOUS METEORITE IMPACTORS: IMPLICATION FOR PLANETARY CHEMISTRY

George Cooper^{1*}

¹NASA-Ames Research Center, MS 239-4, Moffett Field, California, USA

Abstract

From the beginning of the solar system an important source of organic material for all planetary surfaces is likely to have been carbonaceous meteorites (CM) impactors derived from asteroids. Organic material has been detected within the solar system in planetary satellites, comets, interplanetary dust particles, and other material (Pizzarello et al., 2006 and references therein; Glavin et al., 2018). How would the material in CM be differentiated from that in other impactors or indigenous material on Earth? What subsequent effects would it have on planetary chemistry and life? The organic content of CM is high relative to total carbon and is complex in composition; in some classes of CC it consists almost exclusively of an insoluble kerogen-like material or “insoluble organic matter (IOM)”, Fig. 1. The IOM range across individual CM is generally ~70% – 99% of all organic carbon. Also present are simpler soluble compounds ranging from polar amino acids and polyols to nonpolar hydrocarbons. Extensive laboratory analyses (including isotopic) of CM show that their organic material possesses distinct properties inherited from pre-solar sources. These properties should be recognizable on the surface of the modern Earth. I will present the distribution and properties of CM organic matter from decades of accumulated laboratory data.

Figure 1. An estimated structure of the major phase of organic material in carbonaceous meteorites: the insoluble organic matter (Pizzarello and Shock, 2010).

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Keywords: Carbonaceous, meteorites, asteroids.

*Corresponding author: george.cooper@nasa.gov

Meteorites - properties and flux

Keynote 2

16. ONSET OF A HEAVY BOMBARDMENT ON THE EARTH

1.4 GA AGO

A. Lagain^{1,2*}, M. Brož³, J. H. Fairweather², P. Vernazza⁴, Y. Quesnel¹, A. Licht¹,
A. Morbidelli^{5,6}, K. Servis^{4,7}, A. Ozerov⁸, P. Bland² and G. K. Benedix².

¹Aix-Marseille Univ., CNRS, IRD, INRA, CEREGE, Institut Origines, Aix en
Provence, France. ²Space Science and Technology Centre, Curtin
University, Perth, Western Australia, Australia.

³Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic.

⁴Aix-Marseille Univ., CNRS, CNES, LAM, Institut Origines, Marseille, France.

⁵Université Côte d'Azur, Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur, CNRS,
Laboratoire Lagrange, France.

⁶Collège de France, CNRS, PSL Univ., Sorbonne Univ., Paris, 75014, France,
Paris, France.

⁷Pawsey Supercomputing Centre, CSIRO, Kensington, Western Australia.

⁸University of California, Berkeley, California, USA.

Abstract

Earth's geological record and impact history have been largely erased by erosion and crustal recycling driven by plate tectonics. As a result, most evidence of ancient impact events and their consequences has disappeared [1-4]. Reconstructing Earth's bombardment history is essential to understanding what makes our planet uniquely habitable. Because the Moon is geologically less active and shared the same collisional environment as Earth, its cratering record offers a window into the history of impacts in the Earth-Moon system. Current models suggest that the period following planetary accretion experienced an impact flux at least four orders of magnitude higher than today's rate, involving a much larger proportion of massive impactors (e.g., [6-7]), after which the flux declined and stabilized around 3 Ga ago [5, 6, 8]. However, the steady-state impact flux over the past 3 billion years is poorly constrained by lunar crater chronology and appears inconsistent with dynamical models of Near-Earth Objects populations [10-11].

In this study, we investigate the impact flux evolution by estimating the age of craters >20 km in diameter on the Moon using small craters superposed on their ejecta blanket [5, 12] and identified using a convolutional neural network-based algorithm [13-15]. In parallel, we model the orbital evolution of asteroid fragments formed following major asteroid breakups in the main belt [10-11] to determine the influence of each event in the cratering history of the Moon.

We identify a significant increase in the flux of km-sized impactors between ~1.4 and 0.9 Ga ago, while the flux of meter-sized impactors remained relatively constant. Dynamical simulations allow to link this increase to a major asteroid breakup that formed the Flora family [16]. Extrapolated to the Earth, we find that impactors >1 km struck our planet every 250 kyrs during this interval. Accounting for preserved craton areas, we estimate that ~2000 complex craters remain to be discovered. These findings highlight the need for further multidisciplinary studies to assess the ecological and climatic effects of varying impact flux over geological timescales.

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Keywords: Impact cratering, Impact flux, Asteroid breakup.

*Corresponding author: lagain@cerege.fr

17. IMPACT-INDUCED METAMORPHIC EFFECTS OF HIGH-ALUMINA AUGITE IN LUNAR ANORTHOSITE BRECCIAS FROM CHANG'E6 LUNAR SOILS

Jiawei Zhao¹, Long Xiao^{1*}, Zaicong Wang¹, Xiang Wu¹, Qi He¹

*¹State Key Laboratory of Geological Processes and Mineral Resources,
Hubei Key Laboratory of Planetary Geology and Deep-Space
Exploration, School of Earth Sciences, China University of Geosciences,
Wuhan, 430074, China.*

Abstract

The Chang'E-6 (CE-6) mission successfully returned farside lunar soils composed of lithic and glassy materials shaped by endogenic and exogenic processes, including crustal differentiation, volcanic activity, impact events, and space weathering [1]. Pyroxene, a common mineral in both lunar basaltic and feldspathic samples, serves as a key indicator of magmatic evolution and impact-related modifications [2, 3]. In this study, we examined shock-altered augite clasts within anorthosite breccias from the CE-6 samples, revealing a suite of deformation and alteration features: shock-induced lamellar twinning, thermally driven recrystallization (yielding granular augite with inherited crystallographic orientations), and localized dissociation products (Fe-metal and fayalite). These features collectively record a transition from transient high-pressure deformation to prolonged high-temperature alteration. Furthermore, the recrystallized augite granules exhibit elevated alumina contents (>8 wt%), indicating intergranular diffusion between augite and plagioclase. This process likely occurred within a large-scale impact melt lake, where slow cooling from ~1300 to 900 °C over several thousand years preserved these signatures. These findings provide critical insights into the thermal evolution of major impact basins, such as the Apollo Basin at the CE-6 landing site, and underscore the role of impact processes in modifying lunar crustal materials.

Objectives and Methods: This study focused on four anorthosite breccias (200–300 μm in size) extracted from the CE-6 lunar soil sample

(CE6C0200YJFM003). To characterize their microstructures and compositions, we employed a multi-technique analytical approach, including: Backscattered electron (BSE), electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD), electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), Kikuchi diffraction (TKD) and scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM).

Key findings: The four anorthosite breccias exhibit similar lithology, consisting predominantly of plagioclase (86.9–92.3 vol%) and pyroxene (7.7–13.1 vol%), with minor accessory phases (<1 vol%) including ilmenite, fayalite, and Fe-metal/oxides. Most augite clasts display granular textures composed of 1–10 μm subgrains while retaining angular to irregular outlines, all showing characteristically high Al_2O_3 (>8 wt%) but low Na_2O (<0.3 wt%) contents. Adjacent augite granules exhibit twin relationships involving 180° rotation around <001> with (100) twin planes, while some clasts locally preserve lamellar (100) twins. Vermicular to dendritic fayalite grains with interstitial material occur sporadically within pyroxene clasts, occasionally containing $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ Fe-metal particles.

Significances: (1) The development of lamellar mechanical twins in augite provides direct evidence of shock deformation followed by thermal recrystallization, documenting the transition from high-pressure to high-temperature conditions. (2) The dissociation sequence of Mg-rich augite \rightarrow fayalite \rightarrow Fe-metal phases demonstrates a clear thermal metamorphic origin, distinguishing this process from space weathering effects. (3) Elevated alumina contents (>8 wt%) in augite reflect intergranular diffusion from plagioclase rather than primary crystallization during the solidification of lunar magma ocean, indicating slow cooling (likely over millennia) within an impact melt sheet.

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Keywords: shock twinning, augite recrystallization, thermal dissociation, shock cooling history

*Corresponding author. Longxiao@cug.edu.cn

18. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF A METEORITE COLLECTION FROM EGYPT

Bassem S. Nabawy¹

¹*Department of Geophysical Sciences, National Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt.*

Abstract

This presentation documents the meteoritic collection of Egypt, housed in the Egyptian Geologic Museum. A total of 54 meteorites have been gathered from various sites worldwide. These meteorites convey information from outer space to various locations on Earth. They vary in content and classification, encompassing iron-nickel, chondrites, achondrites, stony-metallic, pallasites, and others. The chemical composition of the meteorite collections was examined in situ using portable micro-XRF, revealing a spectrum of major and minor elements quantified in % and ppm, respectively. Additionally, the electrical properties were assessed, encompassing electrical conductivity (σ), dielectric constant (ϵ'), and dielectric loss (ϵ'') across a frequency spectrum from 4 Hz to 8 MHz. The data obtained were displayed as a function of electric frequency, facilitating the matching of the electric fingerprint. Additionally, the thermal conductivity of certain meteorites was assessed, revealing their thermal conductivity (T_c), effusivity (e), diffusivity (a), and heat capacity (C_p).

**Corresponding author: bs nabawy@yahoo.co.uk*

19. CHARACTERIZATION OF ABA PANU METEORITE FALL SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA

Olugbenga Okunlola*,¹Albasher Gismelssed,² Mathew Oyedokun,¹Ahmed Al-Rawas,² Ali Yousif,² Jacob Adetunji, ³, Hishen Widatalla,² Mohammed Elza,²

¹ *Department of Geology; University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria*

² *College of Science, ,Physics Department; Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Sultanate of Oman*

³ *School of Environmental Sciences, University of Derby, Kedleston Road DE22 1GB, UK*

Abstract

X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fields Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) with EDS and Mössbauer Spectroscopy (MS), were applied to investigate a newly fallen solid piece of debris named the Aba Panu meteorite, after a city in south western Nigeria (Lat: N 08° 14' 25.7" and Long: E 003° 33' 47.0"). Matching X-ray diffraction results, together with the FE-SEM analysis confirms the presence of four kinds of iron-bearing minerals, namely olivine, pyroxene, kamacite (Fe-Ni alloys) and troilite (FeS). The Mössbauer spectra recorded at 295 K and 78 K consist of two strong paramagnetic doublets emanating from olivine of quadrupole splitting 2.9 mm/s and pyroxene of quadrupole splitting 2.1 mm/s. These are superimposed on two magnetic sub-spectra attributed to kamacite and troilite phases. From the Mössbauer sub-spectra absorption area, the ratio of the olivine absorption area to the pyroxene absorption area indicates that the meteorite can be classified as an L-ordinary chondrite. The mole fraction of the Fe end-member of olivine (fayalite) and the orthopyroxene (ferrosilite) calculated from the EDS data was used to identify the petrographic type of the meteorite.

Keywords: Meteorites. Ordinary chondrite , Kamacite, Mössbauer, FE-SEM, Petrologic type

Corresponding author: gbengaokunlola@yahoo.co.uk

Solar System exploration

Keynote 3

20. POSSIBLE IMPACT SPHERULE BEDS OBSERVED BY PERSEVERANCE ROVER ON THE RIM OF JEZERO IMPACT CRATER

N. Mangold^{1*}, E. Dehouck², C. Quantin-Nataf², A. Udry³, O. Forni⁴, C. Bedford⁵, S. Schroeder⁶, A. Klidas⁷, D. Flannery⁷, V. Hoogland⁷, Y. Liu⁸, A. Treiman⁹, V. Debaille¹⁰, O. Gasnault¹⁰, S. Le Mouélic¹, R. Barnes¹¹, L.C. Kah¹², E. Ravanis¹³, R. Lorenz¹⁴, J. W. Rice Jr¹⁵, J.I. Simon¹⁶, R.A. Yingst¹⁷, K.M. Stack⁷, A. Cousin¹⁰, J. Hurowitz¹⁸, R. Wiens⁴

¹LPG, CNRS, Nantes Université, Nantes, France, ²LGL, CNRS, UCB Lyon, France
³University of Nevada, Las Vegas, USA ⁴IRAP, Toulouse, France, ⁵Purdue Univ., USA,
⁶DLR-WR, Berlin, Germany, ⁷Queensland Univ., Brisbane, Australia, ⁸JPL/Caltech, Pasadena, USA, ⁹Lunar and Planetary Institute (USRA), 3600 Bay Area Blvd., Houston TX 77058 USA, ¹⁰Université libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, Belgium, ¹¹Imperial College, London, UK, ¹²Department of Earth, Environmental, and Planetary Sciences, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA, ¹³Department of Earth Sciences, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, Hawai'i, ¹⁴JHUAPL, Laurel, Maryland, ¹⁵School of Earth and Space Exploration, Arizona State University, Tempe, USA, ¹⁶ARES, NASA Johnson Space Center, Houston, USA, ¹⁷PSI, Tucson, AZ 85719, ¹⁸Stonybrook University, New York, USA

Abstract

Rock chemistry, mineralogy and textures were investigated as the Perseverance rover traversed the rim of Jezero Crater. A large diversity of both primary and secondary minerals has been encountered close to the top of the rim, and going down westward down its outer slopes, representing material excavated by Jezero impact. As Jezero crater has been dated to ~3.9 Ga, the rocks excavated are older, Early Noachian or pre-Noachian (>4.0 Ga). At the location named Broome Point, the SuperCam RMI imaged two float rocks with abundant spherical clasts cemented together, which hereafter we refer to as "spherules", a term used here as purely descriptive. Nearby in outcrop, a 10-cm thick layer has been observed with a similar character, i.e. a dense packing of spherules. The statistical assessment of the diameters of these spherules shows that the spherules are ~2-mm diameter on average, with a Gaussian distribution. Individual spherules are closely packed, such that the spherules represent >90% of the particles. Their IR spectra are

anhydrous, distinct from many of the rocks encountered on the rim, and relatively flat, possibly pointing to the presence of glass phases. The bulk composition obtained by averaging several laser points is basaltic and homogeneous, and similar to the surrounding fine-grained bedrock. Another location 50 m away to the North named Dennis Pond displays smaller spherules (<1 mm) scattered in several laminae. While no abrasion and use of proximity science was possible at Broome Point, Dennis Pond instead offered a favourable location for enabling a chemical analysis by the PIXL instrument. The composition of the eight spherules analysed there show rims distinct from the interior, and diverse compositions including plagioclase and pyroxene. Overall, from their composition, distribution and context, these spherules are distinct in shape and context to sedimentary concretions observed at both Meridiani Planum and Gale crater, opening two potential hypotheses for their formation: explosive volcanism or impact ejecta. A volcanic context may reasonably explain the presence of spherical clasts as accretionary lapilli made by explosive volcanism, and the similarity in composition of surrounding rocks could suggest a similar origin for surrounding layers. Nevertheless, the homogeneity of the spherule size diameter and their well-defined sphericity are not classical characteristics for volcanic lapilli, which are usually heterogeneous in shape and size on Earth. In contrast, impact spherules observed on Earth are specifically spherical. At Dennis Pond, the various composition of spherules are difficult to explain in a volcanic context. Assuming an impact origin, spherules of these sizes, on Earth, would derive from impacts >1000 km away. Although a potentially thinner atmosphere may enable a closer provenance, it is unlikely that Jezero crater would be the source neither the nearby impact basin of Isidis basin. Nevertheless, the timing within the enhanced bombardment of the pre-Noachian period opens many options for the source crater, including some that are now buried within the northern plains. If this hypothesis was confirmed, spherule beds on the outer rim of Jezero crater would represent a unique location to study this ancient period.

Keywords: Mars, Perseverance, Jezero crater, spherules

*Corresponding author: nicolas.mangold@univ-nantes.fr

21. FROM IMPACT TO DEPOSITION: MARTIAN CRATERS AS SEDIMENTARY THEATERS OF A ONCE-FLUVIAL PLANET

Wassim Fitouri*

*'Université de Tunis El Manar, Faculté des Sciences de Tunis,
Département de Géologie, Campus Universitaire, 2092 Tunis, Tunisie*

Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive analysis and classification of Martian sedimentary environments, focusing on deltaic and alluvial systems in a tectonically inactive context. Utilizing high-resolution satellite imagery, digital elevation models (MOLA DEM), and advanced GIS tools (ArcGIS, Jmars, HiView, Mars QuickMap), more than 313 sedimentary systems were identified, based on previous works (Cabrol and Grin, 2001; Fassett and Head, 2007; Seybold et al., 2007; Kraal et al., 2008; Fassett and Head, 2008; cabrol and Grin, 2010; Kleinhans, 2010; Kleinhans et al., 2010; Di Achille and Hynek, 2010; De Villiers et al., 2013; Hauber et al., 2013; R. et al., 2014; Irwin et al., 2015; Palucis et al., 2016; Horvath and Andrews-Hanna, 2017; Grindrod et al., 2018; Hughes et al., 2019; Wilson et al., 2021; De Toffoli et al., 2021) and new observations, those systems were mapped, and morphologically characterized. We propose a detailed classification of Martian deltas into three main types: progradational, aggradational-progradational, and terraced deltas (shown in the map below), each reflecting distinct depositional dynamics and paleoenvironmental conditions. Stratigraphic markers such as cross-bedding, channels, and terraces were used to infer sedimentary processes influenced by water flow, impacts, and volcanism. These findings provide critical insights into Mars' hydrological history, the extent and duration of past water bodies, and the potential habitability of the planet. The methodology developed offers a framework applicable to sedimentological studies on other planetary bodies, enhancing our understanding of planetary surface evolution and guiding future astrobiological exploration.

Keywords: Mars, deltaic systems, alluvial deposits, sedimentology, paleoenvironment, remote sensing, planetary geology

*Corresponding author: fitouri.wassim@etudiant-fst.utm.tn

22. PLANETARY DEFENSE AND SOME ASPECTS OF THE ESA HERA SPACE

MISSION

Christian Koeberl^{1*}, Maria del Pilar Caballo Perucha², Gerhard Paar², and Christoph Traxler³

¹*Department of Lithospheric Research, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria*

²*Joanneum Research, Institute for Digital Technologies, 8010 Graz, Austria*

³*VRVis GmbH, 1220 Vienna, Austria*

Abstract

As impact events are known to have severe effects on the geological and biological evolution of the Earth, the need to detect potentially hazardous objects that might collide with the Earth, and to potentially protect our planet from asteroid impacts, has been recognized in recent years. For example, 66 million years ago the Chicxulub impact had a devastating influence on the biosphere, causing a severe mass extinction. The most iconic species that has fallen victim to the impact, the dinosaurs, literally had no chance.

Today, we have a technological society with a lot of relevant knowledge. Potentially dangerous asteroids are known, as is technology to possibly slightly alter the orbits of such near-Earth objects (NEOs), termed “planetary defense”. Two main options related to the discovery of a potentially dangerous impactor have been discussed, one where the NEO is discovered several years before collision, which presents a chance to use (future) technology to potentially alter the course of the object to avoid impact, or alternatively that a (maybe smaller) object is only detected weeks or days before impact, which just gives the chance to refine the calculations of the impact location, leaving possibly enough time to evacuate an area. A related issue involves communication and warning in case of any danger, particularly these days when mistrust in authorities and science is increasing. Recently there are attempts to bring this discussion to a wider public as part of the recently declared United

Nations (UN) “International Year of Asteroid Awareness and Planetary Defense” in 2029.

As part of the planetary defense efforts, the European Hera spacecraft, launched in October 2024, will study the Didymos binary asteroid system that was impacted four years earlier by the NASA Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) spacecraft. These studies contribute to the validation of the kinetic impact method to deviate a near-Earth asteroid from a colliding trajectory with Earth. Among other goals, it will measure the size and morphology of the crater created by the DART impact, characterize the composition and physical properties of the binary asteroid system, as well as the sub-surface and internal structures of these objects. Open questions include the size and shape of the crater left by the DART impact, or if the entire asteroid underwent reshaping, as well as the mineralogy, structure and precise mass of Dimorphos. The contribution of our team to the Hera mission mainly consists of supporting the various scientific camera instrument teams by reconstructing, visualizing, analyzing, and managing in 3D, the data acquired with the different instruments on board. For this purpose, the 3D-GIS functionality is developed for the planetary 3D viewer PRo3D, which had been developed by the Austrian team earlier and used for, e.g., the Mars-2020 mission, but also for the March 2025 Mars flyby of the Hera spacecraft; the new tools will be fully available before the Hera rendezvous with the Didymos asteroid system in late 2026.

Keywords: Planetary Defense, Impact Danger

**Corresponding author: christian.koeberl@univie.ac.at*

23. PHASE A FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A SECOND LAGRANGE POINT MARS OBSERVATORY: GLOBAL ATMOSPHERIC ESCAPE, AURORA AND RECONNECTION INVESTIGATION

Jennifer A. Darko^{*}

*¹Department of Space and Climate Physics, University College London,
London, United Kingdom*

This project explores the feasibility of an observatory mission to the second Lagrange point (L2) of Mars, with the scientific goal of developing the knowledge of Martian atmospheric escape, magnetospheric interactions, and planetary evolution. The mission responds to the limitations of Earth-based observations, where distance, atmospheric absorption, and temporal restrictions hinder long-term and high-resolution monitoring of Mars. By positioning an observatory at Mars' L2 point, which is an unexplored perspective, the mission would provide continuous coverage of the planet and enable in situ measurements of the Mars magnetotail. The objectives of the study were to evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of a Mars L2 mission compared with ground and orbital alternatives; to identify the environmental and engineering factors that constrain such a mission, including launch vehicle capacity, radiation exposure, and communication challenges; and to design a concept for an observatory optimized for scientific return while remaining feasible under current technological and budgetary limitations.

The methods combined literature-based research, calculations of orbital mechanics and power availability, and preliminary spacecraft sizing and design trade-offs. Particular attention was given to the electromagnetic spectrum accessible at Mars L2, the crustal magnetic field environment, and the implications of Mars' rotation for temporal observation strategies. The findings indicate that, despite higher costs and technical demands relative to ground-based facilities, an observatory at Mars L2 offers unique opportunities. It would enable continuous monitoring of atmospheric dynamics, direct measurements of space weather effects

on Mars, and comparative studies with Earth's own magnetospheric system. These data would improve understanding of how planetary atmospheres evolve under solar wind forcing, helping to answer the fundamental question of why Mars lost much of its atmosphere while Earth retained a stable, habitable environment.

The significance of this study lies both in its potential scientific contributions to planetary science and exploration. Scientifically, the mission aligns with the European Space Agency's Voyage 2050 [1] priority themes on magnetospheric systems and planetary evolution, and objective 3 of the African Space Policy [2]. Strategically, it demonstrates that extraterrestrial robotic exploration, particularly from novel orbital positions, is well within reach of the global scientific community, including Africa. By engaging with ambitious planetary missions, African researchers and institutions can position themselves at the forefront of planetary sciences, contributing to discoveries about Mars that could help us understand the evolution of Earth and the solar system.

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Keywords: Exploration, Mars, Lagrange, Atmosphere, Magnetotail

**Corresponding author. jennifer.darko06@gmail.com*

24. STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A 1P POCKETQUBE SATELLITE FRAME

Solomon K. Appekey¹, Daniel Asante¹, Lazar Jeftic¹, Jake Yawson¹, Selorm Appekey¹

¹Xavier Space Solutions; Block A, Aurora Apartments, Water works, 37 - Accra

Abstract

This paper details the structural design and comprehensive analysis of a 1p PocketQube satellite frame intended for deployment from the Alba Orbital deployer (AlbaPod). This frame was designed as part of Ghana's first locally designed and manufactured PocketQube satellite - XavSat-1. The design focuses on ensuring the frame's structural integrity and survivability during launch. To this end, a series of critical structural analyses were performed in strict compliance with the SpaceX Falcon 9 Payload Rideshare User Guide (RPUG). These analyses include a static structure to assess its response to pre-defined quasi-static loads, a random vibration analysis to characterize its resilience against launch vibrations and a response spectrum to predict its dynamic behaviour. The results of these analyses demonstrate that the proposed PocketQube frame design is robust and fully compliant with the mechanical and dynamic requirements for safe and reliable launch into orbit. This work provides a detailed methodology for the structural verification of the XavSat-1 PocketQube frame.

Keywords: XavSat-1, PocketQube satellite, AlbaPod, quasi-static load, random vibration, response spectrum.

*[*Corresponding author. appekeysolomon@gmail.com](mailto:appekeysolomon@gmail.com) or pyska@leeds.ac.uk*

25. THE AFRICAN SPACE STATION PROJECT: BRIDGING THE GAP IN SPACE SCIENCE EDUCATION WITH A VIRTUAL LEARNING PLATFORM FOR STUDENTS IN AFRICA.

Joshua Uzochukwu¹, Idris Mubaraq², Ernest Matey^{3*}, Anita Antwiwaa⁴,
Joseph Quansah⁵,
Bright Ayenor⁶, Uzochukwu Dunamis⁷, Godfred Ayenor⁸

All Nations University Space Systems Technology Laboratory, Off
Akwadum Road, Koforidua, Eastern Region, Ghana

Abstract

Despite a growing interest in space technology across Africa, a critical problem persists: the lack of accessible, hands-on, and scalable space science education. Traditional programmes are often hindered by prohibitive costs, limited infrastructure, and a shortage of trained instructors, creating significant barriers for millions of aspiring students. The African Space Station (ASS) Project, an initiative launched by the All Nations University in Ghana, directly confronts this challenge. By combining online accessibility with practical, scalable instructions, the project is designed to deliver hands-on satellite engineering education to one million students across the continent. It aims to equip them with real-world skills in space science, satellite systems, and engineering innovation, irrespective of geographic, economic or language barriers.

At its core, the ASS Project is a virtual learning platform providing interactive and intuitive learning models. This platform guides students from absolute beginners to advanced learners through key concepts, including orbital mechanics (this involves understanding the principles governing the motion of satellites and spacecraft in orbit around Earth or other celestial bodies), satellite subsystem, telemetry (telemetry refers to the process of collecting and transmitting data from a satellite or spacecraft back to Earth. This data can include information about the satellite's health, its position, and scientific data from its payload), space

to ground, radio communication, amateur satellite services, antenna design, modulation techniques, data encoding and decoding (SSTV (Slow Scan Television) and morse code), and protocols for reliable data exchange, crucial for receiving its data.

A key entry point is a comprehensive instructional guide that enables students and educators to launch school-based space programme using the free, online tools (<https://sstl.anuc.edu.gh/african-space-station-project>) and curriculum provided. Upon completing the programme, participants can take a certification exam; to date, over 1400 students have successfully participated.

The programme's reach is already continent-wide, with participants from 18 African countries, including Angola, Benin, Egypt, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Morocco, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, South Sudan, Tanzania, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

A common issue is the fact that various African countries speak different languages, creating a barrier to space education. This project aims to counter this issue by providing space science education in different languages. The African Space Station Project is being translated into common African languages such as English, French, Portuguese, Arabic, Swahili, Igbo, Afrikaans, Hausa and Spanish.

This paper explores the successes, outlines challenges, and highlights opportunities of the African Space Station (ASS) Project.

Keywords: Space Science Education, Virtual Learning, Satellite Engineering, Africa, STEM

**Corresponding author e-mail address: africastemssatellite@gmail.com*

26. IRON OXIDATION STATE IN IMPACT GLASS SPHERULES FROM THE BOSUMTWI UPPERMOST IMPACT FALLBACK LAYER

Gabriele Giuli^{*}, Maria Rita Cicconi¹, Sigrid G. Eeckhout², Christian Koeberl³,
Bill P. Glass⁴, Giovanni Pratesi⁵

¹*School of Science and Technology–Geology Div., University of Camerino,
Italy*

²*European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), Grenoble, France*

³*Department of Lithospheric Research, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna,
Austria*

⁴*Dept. Geology, University of Delaware, Newark, USA.*

⁵*Dip. Scienze della Terra, University of Firenze, Italy.*

Abstract

During the ICDP drilling campaign of the Bosumtwi crater in 2004, several glass particles were found in the uppermost impact fallback layer cored at borehole LB-05B (6.50052°N, 1.41595°W). The uppermost 5 cm of this impact layer (called I17A1) contained also transparent impact glass spherules, whose geochemistry has already been studied in [1], displaying a variety of surface textures, from shiny to pitted, and internal structure, from homogeneous to vesicular. In order to obtain information on the iron oxidation state of these spherules, we performed micro-XANES measurements.

The samples used for the XANES measurements were prepared as polished spherules embedded in resin. XANES data have been collected at the ID26 beamline of the ESRF storage ring (Grenoble, F) using a Si (311) monochromator. The small X-ray beam size at the sample, ca. 55 x 120 μm, probed only the inner core of these spherules. Accurate analysis of the pre-edge peak energy and integrated intensity, determined $\text{Fe}^{3+}/(\text{Fe}^{2+}+\text{Fe}^{3+})$ ratios on all samples with an estimated error of ±0.05 [2]. XANES data collected on 8 different samples display an excellent signal to noise ratio, allowing for the extraction of information on the Fe oxidation

state from the pre-edge region. The energy and integrated intensity of the pre-edge peak indicate that Fe is mostly divalent in these samples, with $\text{Fe}^{3+}/(\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{3+})$ ratios in the 0.03 to 0.05 ± 0.05 range for 6 samples, and close to 0.1 ± 0.05 for 2 samples. The pre-edge peak intensity is indicative of a coordination number of divalent Fe intermediate between 4 and 5.

We did not find appreciable differences in the Fe oxidation state of spherules having different surface features or different vesicularity. The only particle composed of two welded teardrops, despite being slightly more oxidized than the others, still have a similar Fe oxidation state and coordination environment as all the others. Both Fe oxidation state and coordination environment are similar to those of most tektites studied so far [3,4,5] and to Trinity (atomic bomb) glass [6].

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Keywords: impact glass spherules, XANES

*Corresponding author: gabriele.giuli@unicam.it

27. PRELIMINARY PRESENTATION OF SIX POTENTIAL NEW IMPACT SITES DETECTED BY SYSTEMATIC PROSPECTION OF CIRCULAR STRUCTURES IN MAURITANIA.

E. Ould Mohamed Navee^{1,2*}, D. Baratoux³, H. Chennaoui Aoudjehane^{1,2}, H. Si Mhamdi⁴, and M. Rajji⁵

¹*GEOOPEN, Laboratory, Hassan II University of Casablanca, Faculty of Sciences Ain Chock Casablanca, Morocco.* ²*ATTARIK Foundation for Meteoritics and Planetary Science, Hassan II University of Casablanca.* ³*Geosciences Environnement Toulouse, University of Toulouse, Research Institute for Development & CNRS, 14, Avenue Edouard Belin, 31400 Toulouse, France.* ⁴*Department of Geosciences, Faculty of Sciences and Technics, Moulay Ismail University, Errachidia 52000, Morocco.* ⁵*Hassan II University of Casablanca, Faculty of Science Ben M'Sik, Department of Geology, Laboratory of Sedimentary Basins Dynamics and Geological Correlation, Casablanca, Morocco*

Mauritania, characterized by its ancient (Archean to Paleoproterozoic) desert terrains and gentle relief, remains under-explored regarding impact structures. Prior to this work, only two confirmed impact craters, Tenoumer and Aouelloul, and four additional circular structures with suspected impact origins had been identified within the country. This study presents a systematic exploration of circular structures across Mauritania, aiming to build a comprehensive database to support their investigation and assess their origins. The methodology combined a multi-scale analysis of Google Earth imagery and Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), along with a preliminary evaluation based on geomorphological features and available geological maps and data.

This nationwide survey led to the detection of 50 new circular structures [1]. These features are scattered throughout Mauritania, with a notable concentration in the Phanerozoic terrain. Their diameters range from 60 meters to 7.5 kilometers, following a right-skewed distribution. Based on this assessment, a non-impact origin appears most plausible for 48 of the identified structures. However, six structures (Chegga 2, Dio Bou Guedra, Temimichat Ghallaman, Rachid, Tichit, and Hassi Djebilet 2) warrant further investigation. One of these, Temimichat Ghallaman, has already been visited in the field by our team, but no definitive conclusion could be reached. This presentation provides a preliminary classification of these circular features and highlights the most promising candidates for potential meteorite impact sites to guide future field research.

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*Corresponding author: elycheikhnaviee@gmail.com

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